

RESCUER

<https://rescuerproject.eu/>

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The consortium

No	Name	Short name	Country
1	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM	Spain
2	ENGINEERING - INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA SPA	ENG	Italy
3	CS GROUP-FRANCE	CS GROUP-FRANCE	France
4	THEON AISTHITHIRES MONOPROSOPI A EVE	THEON	Greece
5	BRAGI GMBH	BRAGI GmbH	Germany
6	PANEPISTIMIO DYTIKIS ATTIKIS	UNIWA	Greece
7	UNIVERSITY OF GREENWICH	UoG	United Kingdom
8	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	Greece
9	INOV INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES, INOVACAO	INOV	Portugal
10	DEUTSCHES ZENTRUM FUR LUFT - UND RAUMFAHRT EV	DLR	Germany
11	Elliniko Idryma Evropaikis kai Exoterikis Politikis (HELLENIC FOUNDATION FOR EUROPEAN AND FOREIGN POLICY)	ELIAMEP	Greece
12	SERVICE DEPARTEMENTAL INCENDIE ET SECOURS DE LA SAVOIE	SDIS	France
13	I.S.A.R. GERMANY STIFTUNG GGMBH	ISAR GERMANY	Germany
14	SERVICIO MADRILENO DE SALUD	SERMAS	Spain
15	COMUNIDAD DE MADRID	GERA	Spain
16	ISEM-INSTITUT PRE MEDZINARODNU BEZPECNOST A KRIZOVE RIADENIE, NO	ISEMI	Slovakia
17	ELLINIKI OMADA DIASOSIS SOMATEIO	HRT	Greece
18	OSTERREICHISCHES ROTES KREUZ	ARC	Austria
19	ECOLE NATIONALE SUPERIEURE DES OFFICIERS DE SAPEURS-POMPIERS (ENSOSP)	ENSOSP	France
20	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	VICOM	Spain

The project

RESCUER aims to design and develop a First-Responder-centered technology toolkit that will empower the next generation of First Responders (FR) by enhancing their operational capacity and safety, specifically in adverse conditions, both environmental and infrastructure-wise.

Adopting the "HERO" (enHanced nEw eRa first respOnder) concept, RESCUER will deliver a toolkit offering:

1. Sense augmentation,
2. Precise and infrastructure-less self-positioning,
3. Cognitive support and multi-sense AR interfaces,
4. Robust ad-hoc intra-team communications for both verbal and data exchanges.

RESCUER will also introduce the capability of extracting environment information "in situ and infrastructure-wise.

Our vision

Augmenting FRs' senses

including vision (especially in adverse conditions such as darkness, rain, or fog), hearing, detection of victims and detection of unseen hazards such as obstacles or dangerous gases.

Precise self-localization

in indoor or outdoor environments, using multiple technologies and modes for accuracy and robustness.

Cognitive support

measuring the cognitive load of each FR and automatically deciding how much of the available information to display so as to avoid distraction and mental fatigue.

Situational awareness

merging all of the previous in innovative augmented reality information displays.

Tools and solutions

Positioning and orientation capabilities

Visual based self-localization: One of the main needs of FRs while operating is the ability to accurately identify their location at any type of environment including commercial or residential buildings and underground places (e.g. mines, subway systems, caves etc.) in real time.

Augmented tools for enhancing sensing capabilities

Robust vision in adverse conditions: RESCUER will provide augmented vision modules for cancelling of adverse weather and environmental conditions, exploiting the benefits of Artificial Intelligence and Deep Learning.

Ad hoc communication network: In the context of RESCUER, the exchange of data and interaction between modules of the AR tools is of paramount importance. The exchange of data/information is one of the main pillars of the envisaged RESCUER solution. In environments like the ones in the scope of the project one must assume that no communications infrastructure will exist and so the communications should be established in an ad-hoc mode to supply the communications required.

Perception tools

Cognitive load balancing: Suboptimal levels of cognitive functioning (e.g., increased workload, inattention and fatigue) constitutes a primary factor of poor performance and increased number of accidents in risky environments. For this reason, RESCUER will equip FRs with specialized health monitoring systems able to keep track of their vital signs and constantly assess their cognitive state to prevent risky behaviours and always operate in optimal psychophysical conditions.

Technologies

Technology/tool	Start TRL	End TRL
Helmet-Mounted Display	4	6
Long-Wave IR Camera	4	6
Augmented Reality Interfaces	4	6
Smart processing and battery pack	2	6
Augmented vision	3	5
Enhanced hearing	3	6
Augmented olfaction, radar sensing and remote touching	3	5
Signs of life detection	2	4
Visual based self-localization	3	5
Inertial based localization	3	6
Galileo based localization	4	6
Cognitive load balancing	2	5
Information prioritization	4	6
Perception of wireless devices for victim localization	4	6
Ad hoc communication network	5	6
Data sharing orchestration	4	6

- Protocol colors
- 3G/4G
 - Bluetooth
 - WiFi
 - Zigbee/Zwave
 - Wired

Roadmap

Evaluation in pilots

Pilot site	1 st pilot	2 nd pilot
Training Base of Weeze (Earthquake incident)	24-27 November 2022	18-21 April 2024
Tunnel close to Maurienne Valley (Hazmat incident)	27-30 March 2023	20-23 May 2024
Navacerrada's mountains (Mountain rescue)	16-19 January 2023	4-7 March 2024

Earthquake incident (Germany)

The first use case regards a magnitude 7.8 earthquake, lasting approximately 2 minutes, hit the central area of Rhinelandia.

The involved first responders will be trained in the use of the assigned RESCUER tools before testing and using them during the pilot as an important objective of the pilot organization and execution

The goal of the pilot organization is in the one hand the allocation of realistic conditions for the training, test and evaluation but on the other hand also the arrangement of manageable conditions according the TRL of the tools.

Hazmat incident (France)

International crash scenario suspected to be an act of terrorism involving a van transporting ammonia material, a fire starts, with heavy smoke filling the tunnel and the hazmat materials are exposed.

RESCUER will aid operations through:

- its augmented senses modules that will help in identifying hazmat sources, as well as victims through super-hearing by augmenting human voices.
- The ad-hoc network that will be established through the FRs' mobile phones, will allow for intercom through the hearables, as well as inter-team localisation in no visibility settings through inertial, Galileo or fused localisation.
- As the environment is very loud, medics rely on their hearables to filter, magnify and process auditory information, while the first line FRs will be directed to victims through their AR displays, where the different victim and hazmat detection technologies will overlay their information.

Mountain rescue (Spain)

A group of hikers gets lost in the middle of nowhere when suddenly the weather conditions dramatically change and additionally; one of them is injured.

Once the emergency services are notified, a helicopter search-and-rescue group (GERA) takes control of the rescue plan and the local health emergency services (SERMAS) is also notified.

In these harsh but realistic conditions, RESCUER technologies will assist the FRs:

- Enhanced hearing will reduce the roar of the helicopter during transit and the noise of the rain on the ground
- Novel map-based localisation will be available through helmet-mounted cameras, with lightweight de-raining algorithms ensuring its robust operation.
- Considering that FRs' will be assisted by RESCUER's tools and systems functionalities with respect to the perception of wireless devices, the localization of those victims that have been trapped under avalanche or gullies will be considerably expedited, using the electromagnetic trace of the electronic devices that most hikers bear with them.

Opportunities for clustering - dissemination

- Collaboration in the context of Horizon Results Booster
 - Inclusion of project related info and events in our web site
 - Magazine on FR technologies
- Possibilities St**
- **Conference (World forum on IoT: technologies for FRs)**
 - **Special issue on IEEE IT Professional magazine (TBA)**

CALENDAR

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MAY
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MON

[RESCUER Pilot planning meeting - Navacerrada](#)

May 23 - May 25

MAY
24
TUE

[INGENIOUS 1st FSX and 1st International Workshop on "Tools for the First Responder of the Future" - Villejust](#)

May 24 - May 25

JUN
30
THU

[Projects to Policy Seminar \(PPS\) - Brussels](#)

Jun 30 @ 12:00am - Jul 1 @ 12:00am

OCT
26
WED

[8th IEEE World Forum on Internet of Things \(IEEE WFloT2022\) - Yokohama](#)

Oct 26 - Nov 11

FRs' Cutting Edge Technologies Magazine

RESCUER 360
(refs to other
projects)

RESCUER

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